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PREVALENCE OF MIGRAINE AMONG PATIENTS PRESENTING IN THE OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT

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ABSTRACT:

Globally, approximately 15% of people are affected by migraine. It most often starts at puberty and is worst during middle age. As of 2016, it is one of the most common causes of disability. Migraine is a primary headache disorder characterized by recurrent headaches that are moderate to severe. Typically, episodes affect one half of the head, are pulsating in nature, and last from a few hours to 3 days. This cross-sectional study was conducted in the outdoor department of different hospitals. The relevant data i.e. name, age, gender, history of migraine, duration of disease, or any aggravating factors were collected on a predefined proforma. A total of 432 patients were enrolled in this study. The mean age of the patients was 28.34 ± 4.56 years. There were 42% females and 58% males included in this study. The mean age of the male patients was 33.67 ± 2.45 years and the mean age of the female patients was 26.34 ± 4.51 years. There were only 43 (9.95%) patients presenting with the symptoms of migraine. The mean duration of symptoms was 2.34 ± 1.89 years, with a minimum duration of six months and a maximum duration of 5 years.

Keywords: Migraine, Outdoor Patients

INTRODUCTION:

Globally, approximately 15% of people are affected by migraine. It most often starts at puberty and is worst during middle age. As of 2016, it is one of the most common causes of disability. Migraine is a primary headache disorder characterized by recurrent headaches that are moderate to severe. Typically, episodes affect one half of the head, are pulsating in nature, and last from a few hours to 3 days. Associated symptoms may include nausea, vomiting, and sensitivity to light, sound, or smell. The pain is generally made worse by physical activity. Up to one-third of people affected have aura: typically a short period of visual disturbance that signals that the headache will soon occur. Occasionally, aura can occur with little or no headache following it.

Migraine is believed to be due to a mixture of environmental and genetic factors. About two-thirds of cases run in families. Changing hormone levels may also play a role, as

migraine affects slightly more boys than girls before puberty and two to three times more women than men. The risk of migraine usually decreases during pregnancy and after menopause. The underlying mechanisms are not fully known. They are, however, believed to involve the nerves and blood vessels of the brain.

Initial recommended treatment is with simple pain medication such as ibuprofen and paracetamol (acetaminophen) for the headache, medication for the nausea, and the avoidance of triggers. Specific medications such as triptans or ergotamines may be used in those for whom simple pain medications are not effective. Caffeine may be added to the above. A number of medications are useful to prevent attacks including metoprolol, valproate, and topiramate. The purpose of this study was to see the prevalence of migraine in patients presenting in outdoor department. (1-3)

Material of Methods:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the outdoor department of different hospitals. The relevant data i.e. name, age, gender, history of migraine, duration of disease, or any aggravating factors were collected on a predefined proforma after informed consent. This data was analyzed with SPSS version 23.0. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentage. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

A total of 432 patients were enrolled in this study. The mean age of the patients was 28.34 ± 4.56 years. There were 42% females and 58% males included in this study. The mean age of the male patients was 33.67 ± 2.45 years and the mean age of the female patients was 26.34 ± 4.51 years. There were only 43 (9.95%) patients presenting with the symptoms of migraine. The mean duration of symptoms was 2.34 ± 1.89 years, with

a minimum duration of six months and a maximum duration of 5 years.

DISCUSSION:

There are three main aspects of treatment: trigger avoidance, acute symptomatic control, and medication for prevention. Medications are more effective if used earlier in an attack. The frequent use of medications may result in medication overuse headache, in which the headaches become more severe and more frequent. This may occur with triptans, ergotamines, and analgesics, especially opioid analgesics. Due to these concerns simple analgesics are recommended to be used less than three days per week at most.

Worldwide, migraine affects nearly 15% or approximately one billion people. It is more common in women at 19% than men at 11%. In the United States, about 6% of men and 18% of women experience a migraine attack each year, with a lifetime risk of about 18% and 43% respectively.

In Europe, migraines affect 12–28% of people at some point in their lives with about 6–15% of adult men and 14–35% of adult women getting at least one yearly. Rates of migraine are slightly lower in Asia and Africa than in Western countries. Chronic migraine occurs in approximately 1.4 to 2.2% of the population.

These figures vary substantially with age: onset of migraine is most commonly between 15 and 24 years of age, and occur most frequently in those 35 to 45 years of age. In children, about 1.7% of 7-year old and 3.9% of those between 7 and 15 experience migraine, with the condition being slightly more common in boys before puberty. Children as young as two years may be affected. During adolescence, migraine becomes more common among women and this persists for the rest of the lifespan, being twice as common among elderly females than males. In women migraine without aura are more common than migraine with aura; however, in men

the two types occur with similar frequency.

During perimenopause symptoms often get worse before decreasing in severity. While symptoms resolve in about two-thirds of the elderly, in 3 to 10% they persist. (4-7)

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